

Emotional Intelligence and Locus of Control Association with Academic Achievement of Sandwich Students' in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

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Abstract

A student can get admission into a higher institution simply with his/her intelligent quotient but the control and management of emotions (emotional intelligence) and understanding and explaining of success and failures (Locus of control) to a great extent determines his/her academic achievement. This study therefore examined emotional intelligence and locus of Control association with academic achievement of Sandwich students in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Four research questions guided the study. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 150 (70 year 2) and (80 year 3) sandwich students (2018/2019 contact session). No sampling was done because the population is small. 3 sets of instruments were used for the study namely: Emotional Intelligence Self Assessment Instrument (EISAI) adapted from the work of Sterreth (2000), Locus of control Instrument (LOCI) adapted from the work of Levenson (1981) and an achievement test in Educational Psychology constructed by the researchers. Reliability of the instruments were established using Cronbach alpha and an internal coefficient of 0.78 was obtained for EISAI, 0.76 and 0.82 for LOCI subscales namely internal and external locus of control orientation and finally 0.80 for the researchers developed achievement test. The data were analyzed using correlation and regression statistical analysis. The results showed a positive and significant relationship between Emotional intelligence and internal Locus of control and academic achievement of Sandwich students in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Both psychological constructs wheel tremendous influence on the students' academic outcomes. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that lecturers should de-emphasize grades and relative ranking, reward effort rather than ability to help students have internal locus of control orientation and also practical G.S courses that should help students acquire adequate stress management skills should be included in the Sandwich programme to help improve their emotional intelligence.

Key words: Emotional intelligence, Locus of control, Sandwich students', Academic achievement.

Introduction

Education boosts the opportunities for sustainable development and plays a crucial role in the overall development of the individual, society and nation at large. Education is the most important avenue for improving the quality of life of an individuals and his/her adaptation to the society. For this reason, education of every citizen should be taken seriously. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) recognized education as a bedrock of every nations' growth and so outlined clearly in her National Policy on Education (NPE) the national guideline for the effective administration, management and implementation of education at all tiers of government. The Nigerian educational system is structured under the following categories;

- Early child care and development aged 0 to 4 years.
- Basic education aged 5 to 15 years. It encompasses 1 year of pre-primary education, 6 years of primary education and 3 years of junior secondary education.
- Post basic education of 3 years in senior secondary schools and technical colleges and
- Tertiary education provided in colleges of education, polytechnics, monotechnics and the universities.

Sandwich programmes fall under tertiary education. Sandwich programme is a part-time programme for teachers in primary and secondary schools and others to study in the Faculty of Education. All the courses in the Faculty of Education are available during the contact sessions (usually long vocations). Contrary to other academic programmes in the university which has two semesters in a session, sandwich programme has just one contact session. Students are taught by both lecturers in the faculty of education and from the servicing departments. The primary aim of enrolling in any academic programme ranging from primary, secondary to tertiary education is for acquisition of knowledge and skills that will enhance the individuals' fulfillment of his/her potentials as well as psycho-social adjustments in the society. To this end, students' knowledge, understanding, acquisition of facts and skills which is often defined by the educational construct "Academic Achievement" is measured through quiz, assignments and examinations at the end of every contact session.

Psychological constructs such as emotional intelligence and locus of control is vital in explaining students study habits as well as academic outcomes/achievements. Supporting the above statement, Jeanne, Melinda-Smith, Lawrence and Shubin (2021) observed that it is not the brilliant or smartest people who are the most successful or the most fulfilled in life. They argued that some academically brilliant individuals are yet socially inept and unsuccessful at work, in academics or their personal relationships.

This is true because you can get admission into a higher institution simply with your intelligent quotient but control and management of your emotions (Emotional Intelligence) and understanding and explaining your successes and failures (Locus of Control) determines your academic achievement. The researchers' observation of the emotional and social behaviours of sandwich students in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka necessitated the study. Often some of them are tensed up, confused, exhibit aggressive behaviours at the slightest provocation, rude to lecturers, disorganized, fail to do assignment, exhibit low performance in examination, rudely blame lecturers for low grades and inability to complete research projects among others. To buttress this point, some of these sandwich students attend lectures they did not register for, always late to lectures and examinations without any remorse, confused about the correct course outline and ready to exchange words with both classmate and lecturers anytime. This study therefore sought to investigate emotional intelligence and locus of control association with academic achievement.

Emotional intelligence is a psychological construct derived from two terms: Emotion and intelligence. Intelligence belongs to the cognitive (thinking, reasoning) aspect of mental functioning while

emotions belong to the affective (feeling, appreciation) aspect of mental functioning. Simply put, intelligence is the ability to acquire, understand and comprehend information or knowledge as well as being able to transfer the acquired knowledge for problem solving while emotion means state of mood of an individual. Emotions are important pieces of information that tell a person about himself/herself and others but can make one become tensed up, over whelmed and lose control in the face of challenge or stress.

Emotional intelligence is the area of cognitive ability that facilitates interpersonal behaviour. David Goleman, a psychologist and behavioural science journalist popularized the concept of emotional intelligence in the year 1995. In his book titled “Emotional Intelligence”, Goleman explained emotional intelligence as the ability of an individual to appropriately and effectively manage his emotions to ensure those emotions is expressed accordingly. He went further to observe that emotional intelligence is the largest single predictor of success in the workplace. Goleman outlined five categories of emotional intelligence namely: Self-awareness, self regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills.

Some researchers and authors have attempted various definitions of emotional intelligence according to their perspectives. For example, Jeanne et al (2021) explained emotional intelligence as the ability of a person to understand, use and manage his/her emotions in positive ways in order to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and diffuse conflict. According to them, emotional intelligence is commonly defined by four characteristics namely: self awareness, self management, social awareness and relationship management. Navin (2019) assert that emotional intelligence describes the ability, capacity, skill, to identify, assess, and manage ones emotions as well as that of others and groups. Navin observed that emotional intelligence is a critical part of social intelligence which seems to be largely a learned response and continues to develop all through the life span of an individual through relationships and life experiences.

Emotions have a positive intent that serves physical, personal, and social purposes. Ones emotion at a particular time conveys a unique set of identifying signals (emotional information). There are two sides of emotional intelligence namely: High and low emotional intelligence. A student with high emotional intelligence has proper control over his/her emotions and therefore will thrive in the face of any academic complexities while the reverse is the case for a student with low emotional intelligence.

There is an English adage that “Life is not a bed of roses”. All aspects of life including social, religious, marital, economic and educational/vocational is full of challenges, hurdles and problems therefore, a students’ intellectual ability or intellectual quotient is not enough on its own to achieve academic success. This is true because it is the students’ emotional intelligence that will help him/her to manage academic stress and emotions. With the ability to manage stress and stay emotionally balanced, a student can learn to receive upsetting information without letting it upset his/her thoughts, self control and /communications among others.

Psychologically, a student lack of control over his/her emotion may result to some physical health, mental health, relationship and empathy (social intelligence) challenges which ultimately wheels tremendous influence on his/her academic pursuit and performance. To buttress this point, inability to manage emotions equal to not managing of stress which has physical health challenges. This can also impact on a person’s mental health thus resulting in anxiety, tantrum and often depression which are enemies to academic excellence.

Low emotional intelligence affects ones formation of strong relationship which can result to feeling lonely, isolated and inability to engage in collaborative activities. On the other hand (high emotional intelligence) understanding your emotions and how to control them boost social relationship, empowers

you to communicate more effectively, forge stronger relationship, recognize other peoples strengths and weaknesses, embrace adequate social relationship skill and feel loved and happy.

Another psychological construct that is vital in explaining students' academic outcomes is their attribution of success and failure. Weiner (1979, 1980) formulated attribution theory that includes many ideas about achievement motivation and the motivational effects if experiencing success and failures. His theory is directed mainly towards understanding how individuals explain the causes of their successes and failures and how these failures affect their subsequent motivation to achieve. According to attribution theory, persons attribute or scribe the causes of their successes and failures to either external or internal factors. One concept central to attribution theory is "Locus of Control".

In Psychology, locus of control is considered to be an important aspect of personality. Locus of control entails how individuals perceive and explain the underlying factors behind their successes and failures in life. This psychological construct was developed originally by Julian Rotter (1966) and she called it "Locus of Control of Reinforcement". By this name, Rotter was bridging behavioural and cognitive psychology where she affirmed that behaviour was to a great extent guided by reinforcements, and desired/undesired behaviours are strengthen/weaken through rewards and punishments.

Some researchers and authors have attempted various explanation of locus of control. Kendra (2021) noted that locus of control depict the extent to which people feel that they have control over the situations, circumstances and events that influence their lives. Kendra observed that locus of control determines one's response and motivation to event. Neill (2020) noted that locus of control is a determinant of personality and a person's belief that his/her destiny is controlled by internal forces (himself/herself) or by external forces (such as fate, powerful others).

In the context of this research work, the researchers explains locus of control as how people perceive, understand, analyze and infer the causes of their failures and successes in life. In order words, locus of control is an explanation of the results of our actions, whether they are contingent on internal or external control orientations.

By means of observations, tests, quiz and examinations, students' receive feedback concerning their level of performance on tasks either relative to other members of the class or to norm acceptability. This feedback ultimately influences students' perceptions. Locus of control is important in understanding how students' might interpret and use feedback they receive. A person who has an internal locus of control is that person who believes that success or failure is due to his/her own efforts or abilities while a person with external locus of control is more likely to believe that factors such as luck, task difficulty other people's actions cause success or failure.

The above explains why locus of control is important in explaining students' academic achievement. It might not be an over statement to say that psychologically, locus of control seems to be the most predictor of a students' academic achievement after ability. The reason is because students who believe that success or failure in school work is due to external forces (example luck, lecturers' whims) are unlikely to work hard. On the contrary those students' who believe success and failure are primarily dependent on internal forces (their own efforts and abilities) are more likely to work hard.

Psychologically, an individual is more likely to take action to change her situation when the need arises when she holds the view that her destiny lies in her hands and less likely to work toward change when the reverse is the case. Supporting this point, Cheng, Cheung, Chio and Chan (2013) noted that people with an internal locus of control believe their own actions determine the rewards that they obtain while those

with an external locus of control of control believe their actions does not matter much but rather rewards in life are generally outside their control. This matters for academic outcomes/achievements.

The primary aim of enrolling in any academic programme ranging from primary, secondary to tertiary education is for acquisition of knowledge and skills that will enhance the individuals fulfillment of his/her potentials and adjustment in the society. Students' acquisition of knowledge and skills in any teaching and learning activity is measured through quiz, tests, projects and examinations administered by the teacher in-between or at the end of a term, semester or contact session. The extent of the student' performance is simply his achievement.

Academic achievement of students' is one of the vital elements through which the whole education system revolves. Academic achievement is the knowledge acquired and skills developed in school subjects usually by test scores assigned by the teacher. Anierobi, Okeke and Etodike (2021) observed that the evidence of proper teaching and adequate learning should manifest in students' academic achievement. They view academic achievement as the hub around which teaching and learning revolve and therefore, should be the target of every student enrolled in any academic programme. Moore (2019) observed that academic achievement was once thought to be the most important outcome of formal education experiences as well as indicators of students' well-being and psychological development.

Spinath (2012) assert that academic achievement is the most important pre-requisite for individual and societal prosperity as well as a vital issue both for politics and psychological research. In the context of this research work, academic achievement refers to outcomes in performance of students' in intellectual domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor). Some research works including those of Mary (2021), Moore (2019), Sothan (2018), Naila, Muhammad and Ashia (2017) revealed a significant positive association between some psychological constructs like self efficacy, family socio-economic status, students' study habits, and class attendance with academic achievement of students. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, there is paucity of literature on emotional intelligence and students' attribution orientation association to their academic outcomes, hence the need for this study.

Research Questions.

To give direction to this study, the following research questions were posed:

1. What is the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of Sandwich students' in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
2. What is the relative contribution of each of the four attributes of emotional intelligence (Self management, self awareness, social awareness and relationship management) to the academic achievement of sandwich students' in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
3. What is the association between locus of control and academic achievement of sandwich students' in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
4. What is the relative contribution of each of the two dimensions of locus of control (internal and external) to the academic achievement of Sandwich students' in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Method

The research design adopted for this study was correlation survey design. Nworgu (2015) explained that this type of study seeks to establish the relationship that exists between two or more variables. The three variables in the study were: Emotional Intelligence and Locus of Control (independent variables) and Academic achievement of Sandwich students' (dependent variable). The population of the study comprised

150 (year 2 and 3 sandwich students) in 2018/2019 academic session. No sampling was done because the population is small.

Emotional intelligence of the sandwich students' was measured using Sterreth (2000) emotional intelligence instrument. The instrument consists of 20 items structured in a 5-point rating scale of never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), usually (4) and always (5), measuring the four aspects of emotional intelligence namely: self awareness, self management, social awareness and relationship management. In adapting the instrument for the present study, the item scattered in the original instrument was re-arranged to follow a definite pattern to enhance easy analysis. Thus:

- A. Items 1,5,9,12 and 13 becomes items 1,2,3,4 and 5 (for self awareness).
- B. Items 3,6,10,13 and 18 was numbered as items 6,7,8,9 and 10 (for self management).
- C. Items 4,7,14,17 and 19 becomes items 11,12,13,14 and 15 (for social awareness).
- D. Items 2,8,11,16 and 20 was re-written as items 16,17,18,19 and 20.

The minimum score for the scale is 25 while the maximum score is 100. Thus scores of 50 and above will be considered as high emotional intelligence while scores of below 50 (49 downwards) will be considered as low emotional intelligence.

Locus of Control of the sandwich students' was measured using Levenson (1981) locus of control instrument. The instrument consists of 24 items structured in a 6-point likert scale of strongly disagree (1), disagree somewhat (2), slightly disagree (3), slightly agree (4), agree somewhat (5) and strongly agree (6). Originally, this scale consists of 3 sub-scales: Internal locus of control, powerful others and chance. In adapting the instrument for the present study, responses were given on a 4-point likert scale ranging from strongly agree (1), agree (2), strongly disagree (3) to disagree (4). Also, the researchers applied the "Powerful Others" subscale as a measure of external locus of control. The minimum score for the scale is 20 while the maximum score is 80. Thus scores of 40 and above will be considered high while scores below 40 will be considered low.

A researcher constructed achievement test in Educational Psychology (specifically in the area of psychology of learning) titled "Educational Psychology Questionnaire" (EPQ) was used in measuring the students' academic achievement. The instrument was validated by specialists in Educational Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha with overall reliability coefficient of 0.80. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and regression statistical analysis.

Results

Table 1: Pearson Moment Correlation Co-efficient Analysis of Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement of Sandwich Students.

S/N	Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1	Self awareness	12.89	1.92	1				
2	Self management	13.57	1.86	.176	1			
3	Social awareness	13.50	1.43	.235	.307	1		
4	Relationship management	15.07	1.87	.231	.272	.411	1	
5	Academic achievement	55.59	4.13	.579	.642	.712	.636	1

N = 150

Table 1 reveal the relationship between emotional intelligence (Self awareness, self management, social awareness and relationship management) and academic achievement of sandwich students. It reveals that emotional intelligence have a positive relationship (Self awareness: $r = .579$; Self management: $r = .642$; Social awareness: $r = .712$ and Relationship management: $r = .636$) with academic achievement of sandwich students.

Table 2: Regression Table Showing the Relative Contribution of Emotional Intelligence Components(Self awareness, Self management, Social awareness and Relationship management) on Academic Achievement of Sandwich Students.

Variables	B	Std.Error	Beta (B)	T	Sig.	P =
Self awareness	3.70	1.00	0.28	5.33	.000	<0.05
Self management	1.25	0.02	0.44	7.54	.000	<0.05
Social awareness	1.17	0.02	0.41	6.47	.000	<0.05
Relationship management	1.09	0.02	0.39	6.07	.000	<0.05

N = 150

Table 2 shows the 4 components of emotional intelligence and their predictive power on academic achievement of Sandwich students. It revealed that Self management made the highest contribution ($b = 0.44$, $t = 7.54$, $P < 0.05$) followed by Social awareness ($b = 0.41$, $t = 6.47$, $P < 0.05$), Relationship management ($b = 0.39$, $t = 6.07$, $P < 0.05$) and finally Self awareness ($b = 0.28$, $t = 5.33$, $P < 0.05$).

Table 3: Pearson Moment Correlation Co-efficient Analysis of the Relationship Between Locus of Control and Academic Achievement of Sandwich Students.

S/N	Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1	External locus of control	13.14	1.87	1		
2	Internal locus of control	13.19	1.96	.225	1	
3	Academic Achievement	41.42	4.24	.332	.776	1

N =150

Answering research question 3 on what is the association between locus of control components (internal and external locus of control) and academic achievement of Sandwich students, data in table 3 reveal that external locus of control have a negative relationship ($r = .332$) while internal locus of control have a positive relationship ($r = .776$) with academic achievement of Sandwich Students in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Table 4: Regression Table Showing the Relative Contribution of Locus of Control (External and Internal Locus of Control) on Academic Achievement of Sandwich Students.

Variables	B	Std.Error	Beta (B)	T	Sig.	P =
External locus of control	0.23	0.82	0.22	2.76	.006	P>0.05
Internal locus of control	0.64	0.07	0.61	9.17	.000	P<0.05

N =150

Table 4 shows the relative contribution of the dimensions of locus of control (external and internal) to the prediction of academic outcomes of Sandwich students. It revealed that internal locus of control made the highest contribution ($b = 0.61$, $t = 9.17$, $P < 0.05$) while external locus of control ($b = 0.22$, $t = 2.76$, $P > 0.05$).

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement among sandwich students. The reason for this could be attributed to the fact that stress and emotional problems which are enemies of academic success cannot be handled with intelligent quotient but rather “Emotional Quotient”. It also showed that the four components of emotional intelligence (Self management, self awareness, social awareness and relationship management) jointly contributed to the academic achievement of sandwich students and in terms of the magnitude of their contributions, that self management made the highest contribution to the prediction of academic achievement among sandwich students and followed by others in the following magnitude: Social awareness, relationship management and self awareness.

The findings of the study aligned with Jeanne et al (2021) that emotional quotient (intelligence) is what will empower an individual to manage stress and emotions when facing any examination. They further observed

that intelligent quotient and emotional quotient exist in tandem and are most effective when they build off one another. Jeanne et al further emphasized that high emotional intelligence can help an individual navigate the academic challenges. Navin (2019) supporting the above findings noted that emotional intelligence competencies are more important in contributing to work and academic excellence than intelligent quotient and expertise.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that external locus of control have a negative relationship while internal locus of control have a positive relationship on the academic achievement of sandwich students. The reason for this could be that students' are more likely to take action to change their situation when the need arises when they holds the belief that their destiny are in their hands and less likely to work toward change when the reverse is the case. This result is consistent with the existing literature. It agrees with Neill (2020) who observed that it seems to be psychologically healthy to perceive that one has control over those things he/she is capable of influencing. Neill noted that an internal locus of control which he also referred to as "Self agency", "Personal control" and "self determination" is vital for any person desiring any higher attainment in life. Ability and effort attributions are internal to the individual; task difficulty and luck attributions are external. Therefore, students with external locus of control are unlikely to work hard. On the contrary those students who believe that academic failure or success is due primarily to their own effort are more likely to work hard. It also aligns with Kendra (2021) who observed that our anticipation of certain results influences our behaviours and attitudes and thus, a person with internal locus of control orientation is more likely to pursue a goal, stay motivated and thus accomplish the task.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers concluded that emotional intelligence components (Self management, social awareness, relationship management and self awareness) have a joint and separate positive impact on academic achievement of Sandwich students. It also concluded that students with internal attributions to success or failure are more likely to engage on academic task, stay motivated and thus accomplish the desired task while students with external attributions are likely not to work hard and so in summary, external locus of control have a negative relationship while internal locus of control have a positive relationship with academic outcomes of Sandwich students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend as follows:

1. Challenges, hurdles and problems are inevitable in academic pursuit and this exerts some stress on the students thus affecting their emotional intelligence. Psychologically, the first step to improving emotional intelligence is to learn to manage stress. The researchers therefore recommend that the university authority should include as a compulsory subject in Sandwich programme practical GS courses that will help the students' acquire adequate stress management skills.
2. The university authority in collaboration with all stake holders in tertiary education should provide "in-school jobs" for indigent Sandwich students to help them cope with financial hardships which are the major cause of stress especially in Nigeria. By this, the students' should be posted to offices in the university to do some work ranging from sweeping to cleaning, arranging of books among others with a token salary monthly.

3. A common practice in our schools is where lecturers use competitive grading system and make grades public and relative student ranking important. This practice has the effect of making small difference in achievement level seem large so that students who obtain poorest grades may decide they can never learn. In the alternative, when the lecturers de-emphasizes grades and relative ranking but expresses the correct answer so that all students in the class can learn, it helps students see that their chances depend somewhat on their efforts thus developing internal locus of control orientation.
4. To help the students' formation of internal locus of control which is vital for academic success, lecturers should emphasize amount of effort as the cause of success as well as failure, and also reward effort rather than ability in order to motivate all their students to do their best. This can be achieved through the use of individualized instruction were the basis of success is progress at one's level and rate.

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